

Zero Net Deforestation Goal and its effects on the expansion of agriculture land in Mexico

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Executive Summary

This study analyzes the implications that the Zero Net Deforestation Goal (ZDG) in Mexico would have on the production models of the country's 3 main crops (maize, sorghum, sugar cane), focusing on climate, land, energy, and water systems. Using the CLEWs framework and OSeMOSYS tool, three scenarios - Baseline, Zero Deforestation Goal (ZDG) and Restricted Deforestation Goal (RDG) - were modeled to assess the effects of the forest public policy on emissions, land and water demand.

The findings reveal that the ZDG compromises the supply of the crops under study. To meet crop demands it is necessary to expand the agricultural area (RDG scenario), although the decrease in forest cover is smaller than the base case.

1. Introduction

Mexico has 138 million hectares covered by forest vegetation, which among other benefits allows an average absorption of 201.9 million tons of CO₂ equivalent. However, between 2000 and 2024 the forest area registered an average annual deforestation rate of 0.38% (approximately 208,000 hectares).

To protect the country's forest area, Mexico established the Zero Net Deforestation Goal for 2030 (ZDG), with the objective that the number of deforested hectares does not exceed the number of hectares that are reforested naturally or that are assigned for other uses.

The objective of this work is to analyze the implications of the implementation of the ZDG. In particular, the impacts of this initiative on the productive models of three crops: corn, sorghum and sugar cane, in terms of the use of land, energy and water are evaluated. An efficient configuration that allows compliance with the ZGD without compromising the supply of crops is identified.

2. Methodology

In this work, the CLEWs (Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems) framework was applied to model the implications of the zero-deforestation target on climate, land, energy, and water systems. Based on this, a linear optimization model was formulated and solved with the OSeMOSYS (Open Source Energy Modeling System) tool. The Generic Data Kit (GDK) provided within the OSeMOSYS toolkit served as the baseline model to Mexico, agriculture and water data were sourced from Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) databases.

Three scenarios were developed: i) the base scenario that represents the current situation and does not incorporate any measures to contain deforestation in the country,

ii) the zero deforestation goal scenario (ZDG), which sets the country's forest cover during the period analysed (2025-2050), finally iii) the Restricted Deforestation Goal (RDG) allows the use of forest land for agricultural purposes.

The base scenario considers the current forest coverage, equivalent to 640 thousand square kilometers, and the average annual deforestation rate observed between 2000 and 2024 is applied to the study period (2025-2050). The ZDG scenario implies that forest cover will not be less than 640 thousand square kilometers during all the years of study, the demand for agricultural goods for the study period increases in the same proportion as the growth of the population. In the RDG scenario it is assumed that the forest cover cannot be less than 600 thousand square kilometers during all the years of the study. A surplus of 40 thousand square kilometers is set for cropland until 2030, after that year forest cover cannot be reduced

3. Results

This simulation exercise analyses the effects of the Zero Deforestation Goal on production models for maize, sorghum and sugar cane. According to the results:

1. The base scenario presents a gradual reduction in the forest cover area by to 50 thousand square kilometres in favor of an increase in rainfed maize crop.
2. The ZDG scenario is not feasible, this means that the Zero Deforestation Goal public policy and crop supply are incompatible.
3. Restricted Deforestation Goal (RDG) shows the containment of the deforestation process. However, although the forest area is reduced, it does not decrease over time and its size is above the forest cover estimated in the base scenario (10,000 square kilometers against 30,000 square kilometers).

An analysis focused on agricultural production technologies reveals that:

- Neither the rainfed land nor the irrigated land dedicated to corn cultivation suffer changes.
- The irrigated land dedicated to sugar cane decreases while that of sorghum increases.
- The use of water and fuel for growing sorghum increases by 100% and 48% respectively.

Figure 1: Use of irrigated land according to crop

Figure 2: Use of water for agriculture

5. Discussion

Based on the results of this exercise, the goal of zero deforestation cannot be achieved without compromising the supply for the country's three most important agricultural

products. It is necessary to expand crop land, focusing on strengthening irrigated crops, especially sorghum.

The containment of the deforestation process causes an increase in the use of resources (water and fuel) that is associated with a greater area of irrigation fields, which can put pressure on the development of other crops.

Nevertheless, the identification of the crops that increase the irrigated crop area it would allow designing strategies to make the production process more efficient and save resources based on the type of crop.

7. Conclusion

The results suggest the design of strategies to make the irrigated production process more efficient, strengthen and improve existing irrigation systems and increase productivity to limit conversion of forest land.

To deepen the relationship between the goal of zero deforestation and its effects on the agricultural production capacity in the country, as many crops as possible should be included. Model sensitization is require, specifically a precise definition of parameters (irrigation potential and yield rate per crop, regional precipitation rate, etc.).

References

